

B R A I N

**Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence
and Neuroscience**

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About the BRAInitiative

The aim of this journal is to create links between researchers from apparently different scientific fields, such as Computer Science and Neurology. In fact, there are a lot of topics such as Artificial Intelligence, Cognitive Sciences and Neurosciences that can intersect in the study of the brain and its intelligent functions.

Our journal contains (in the BRAINovations and BRAINStorming sections) peer-reviewed articles. These articles should be original, unpublished articles of the authors. The peer review process is a blind one. The reviewers are well recognized scientists who are part of our scientific board, and also independent reviewers.

Some innovative young researchers from around the world had the idea to edit and publish the BRAIN journal in order to make an agora of interdisciplinary study of the brain. Young scientists and seniors in artificial intelligence, cognitive sciences and neurology fields are expected to publish their original works in our journal.

Call for papers

We are seeking papers for our next issue of the BRAIN journal, from academicians, professors, researchers, doctors and clinicians, linguists, psychotherapists, PhD students ... anyone connected to the topics of our journal.

We welcome contributions from all over the world. We plan to put out the next issue (Volume 3, Issue #3) of the BRAIN in August 2012. You are invited to write on any topic of our journal. The deadline for sending articles is **July 10, 2012**. Send your articles to **brain@edusoft.ro** or sign in to use the online system for submitting papers (**www.brain.edusoft.ro**).

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